

Role-Playing as a Therapeutic Tool in the First Psychological Session: An Innovative Approach in Professional Practice

Wendy Milena Serna Llanos

Caribbean University Corporation CECAR, Colombia.

Andrea Marcela Barrios Meza

Caribbean University Corporation CECAR, Colombia.

Patricia María Mendivil Hernández

Caribbean University Corporation CECAR.

Esteban Andrés Pérez Vitola

Caribbean University Corporation CECAR, Colombia.

María José Llanos Orozco

Caribbean University Corporation CECAR, Colombia.

ABSTRACT.

Introduction: This article discusses role-play as a therapeutic tool in the first psychological session with professional practice students, highlighting the importance of an innovative approach to acquiring therapeutic skills. **Methodology:** An innovative role-play strategy was implemented to prepare professional practice students for psychological care of patients and to create a guide for the first psychological session. **Results:** Traceability was obtained from the 2023-I to 2025-I academic periods, with 94 patients treated by students in 2023. In 2024, 91 patients were treated. In relation to the 2025-I semester, 56 patients were treated. This shows that students acquire

therapeutic skills through role-play during classes or individual counseling sessions. Conclusions: The suitability of implementing the first session guide for psychology students and postgraduate students training to become therapists in the clinical field is highlighted.

INTRODUCTION

Role-playing has become an extremely important tool for professionals in training, as it allows them to acquire skills through practice that will be useful for reinforcing knowledge in a safe and controlled environment. Using this technique, trainee psychologists or professionals themselves can simulate questions, put therapeutic skills into practice and make a diagnostic hypothesis. In this sense, one notable aspect of role-play is that people can make mistakes without any risk of affecting patient safety and can correct any shortcomings found in order to integrate both theory and practice. Over time, it allows for the strengthening of personal confidence and communication and therapeutic skills when approaching clinical situations (Ruiz et al. 2018).

Over time and currently, it is clear that the psychological approach requires preparation in therapeutic skills, which is not only theoretical but also practical. Therefore, this article proposes a therapeutic tool such as role-play to learn before the first contact with clients, which is an innovative way of training for the clinical area.

In other words, therapeutic skills play a fundamental role in psychological therapy, as they allow students or professionals to connect with the people they treat. It is not just a matter of diagnosing or intervening, but of how therapists express themselves, ask questions, and organise what patients say in order to understand their current problem and accompanying symptoms. Some studies show that during training, professionals develop these skills through supervised practice, which gradually strengthens their ability to intervene effectively and closely (Páez et al., 2018).

Equally important is the therapeutic alliance, which is a determining factor in getting patients involved in a therapeutic process. In turn, regardless of the approach, the patient-therapist interaction directly influences how the patient perceives the treatment they have received, thus enabling them to express themselves openly and share their personal history, emotions, thoughts and behaviours, among other things. Furthermore, when the patient perceives that the therapist accompanies them without judging them, a trust is generated that facilitates the treatment of their symptoms. All of the above requires commitment, emotional availability, active listening, and clarity in agreements. (Ardito & Rabellino, 2011).

Based on the above, there are theoretical supports that allow for the explanation of the structure that a first session should contain at the beginning of the therapeutic process. Likewise, instructions are proposed taking into account years of experience in clinical supervision of students who are training as psychologists at a higher education university and expertise in working with patients treated by practitioners.

THEORETICAL REFERENCES

The first psychological session serves a dual purpose: to assess the reason for consultation and to establish the foundations of the therapeutic relationship, which conditions adherence and the subsequent therapeutic process (Ottman et al. 2019). In this initial scenario, active and experiential techniques such as role-play can facilitate the exploration of the problem, the observation of live behaviours, and the co-construction of early diagnostic hypotheses, providing complementary information to the clinical history and the patient's account (Otani et al. 2024). In addition, role-play allows for the rehearsal of adaptive responses, the evaluation of social skills, and the promotion of the therapeutic alliance from the first encounter, integrating components of skills training and immediate feedback (Rosenblad et al. 2025).

Although systematic evidence on its effectiveness in the first session is still developing, recent reviews and studies show its usefulness both for clinical training and for the assessment of therapeutic skills and patient outcomes, provided that it is applied within an ethical framework and with informed consent (Ottman et al. 2019; Otani et al., 2024). This article proposes to explore role-play as a therapeutic tool in the first session, describing its theoretical basis, clinical applications, and ethical considerations for its implementation in professional practice. Consequently, the following conceptual foundations, necessary for understanding the role of role-play in the first therapeutic session, will be addressed.

THERAPEUTIC FRAMEWORK

The therapeutic framework constitutes the frame of reference that defines the operating rules of the clinical relationship (schedules, confidentiality, duration, fees, etc.) and is essential for creating a safe environment from the first session onwards. According to Willer (2024), 'the therapeutic frame introduces the limits of the intervention space and facilitates patient safety' (p. 90). Ensuring clarity in the setting in the first session promotes continuity and trust. Therefore, a well-defined frame in the first session is a pillar for the subsequent development of the clinical intervention. Recent studies have shown that role-playing facilitates the observation of interpersonal patterns, the clarification of the reason for consultation, and the assessment of socio-emotional skills (Otani et al. 2024).

GENERAL THERAPEUTIC SKILLS

Therapeutic skills encompass a set of therapist competencies (such as active listening, empathy, formulation, response monitoring, flexibility, and adaptation) that influence psychotherapy outcomes. As Hill and Norcross (2023) point out, ‘researchers have identified multiple therapist skills that are associated with better clinical outcomes, although the evidence for many is still limited’ (p. 409). In their systematic review, they found 10 demonstrably effective skills/methods and four others that are likely to be effective for immediate or medium-term outcomes, highlighting role-playing as one of the demonstrably effective therapeutic skills.

This body of knowledge highlights that therapists not only apply techniques, but also exercise essential relational and operational skills. This implies that, from the first session, therapists must activate these skills to effectively begin the therapeutic process.

FIRST THERAPEUTIC SESSION

The first therapeutic session is a decisive moment for establishing the alliance, clarifying the reason for the consultation, and defining the framework. According to del Río Olvera et al. (2022), the quality of the alliance is established from the first meeting and remains stable during subsequent sessions. Therefore, resources that promote active patient participation are particularly valuable in this initial phase. For this reason, from the first session onwards, it is strategic for the therapist to employ the necessary structures and skills to ensure this relational basis.

Role-playing, when applied carefully and with informed consent, can be used in the first session as a technique for behavioural observation and emotional exploration. Otani et al. (2024) argue that the guided representation of situations in role-playing facilitates the identification of interpersonal patterns and facilitates understanding of the current problem from an experiential perspective, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Process of applying role-playing in the first session.

Initial Session	Role-Playing	Observation	Assessment	Therapeutic Alliance
Gathering basic information	Emotional and behavioural exploration	Identifying interpersonal patterns	Coping styles and understanding the problem	Diagnostic information and connection

Source: adapted from Otani et al. (2024).

This allows the therapist to gather diagnostic information, assess coping styles, and strengthen the therapeutic alliance in real time.

REASON FOR CONSULTATION AND THE PATIENT'S CURRENT PROBLEM

The reason for consultation is understood as the explicit reason why the person is seeking therapy, and it usually manifests itself as a symptom, discomfort, or concern that they perceive in their daily life (García 2024). Although sometimes the patient is unclear about the origin of their discomfort, the professional should facilitate that initial statement and delve deeper into the patient's current problem, that is, the specific situation that affects their functioning, relationships, or emotional state (Gutiérrez 2025).

In clinical practice, early identification of both the reason for consultation and the current problem allows the assessment to be directed, intervention priorities to be established, and the therapeutic framework to be activated from the first session. Based on Berrío-García et al. (2024), they found that the main reasons for consultation were mood problems (29%) and stressful situations, which demonstrates the diversity of demand and the need to articulate it with the current problem. Integrating the reason and the problem into a single block makes it easier for the therapist to treat not only the superficial symptom, but also the context and functional impact of the patient's discomfort.

INITIAL ASSESSMENT, MEDICAL HISTORY, AND DIAGNOSTIC HYPOTHESIS

The initial assessment in the first session involves collecting relevant data from the patient, including personal history, medical history, reason for consultation, and the elements necessary to formulate a preliminary diagnostic hypothesis. The medical history is organised chronologically and includes demographic data, medical and psychological history, reason for consultation, and current symptoms (Borja 2015). At the same time, formulating a temporary diagnostic hypothesis allows the therapist to outline an initial course of intervention and guide the selection of appropriate techniques (Muñoz-Martínez and Novoa-Gómez 2012).

This procedure promotes consistency in the therapeutic process from the outset, enabling both therapist and patient to have a shared reference point of where they are and where they can go. It is particularly important that before each psychological assessment or during the first contact with the patient during the first session, therapists first consider informed consent. After this, the therapeutic framework will facilitate the assessment and formulation of possible diagnostic hypotheses that guide the questions for gathering information about the patient's symptoms or current problem. This ensures ethics and trust for the therapeutic process from the first session.

THERAPEUTIC ALLIANCE AND CLOSURE

The therapeutic alliance is a central factor in psychological therapy, as it is consistently related to treatment outcomes. For example, a meta-analytic synthesis found a mean correlation of $r=0.278$ between alliance and outcome in adult psychotherapy, which shows its relevance even though it is not the only operational factor (Flückiger et al. 2018). In current clinical contexts, establishing the alliance in the first session is key to the continuity and effectiveness of the therapeutic process (Del Río Olvera et al. 2022).

With regard to therapeutic closure, the literature indicates that preparing the patient from the outset for the finitude of the process improves the transition and reduces the negative impact of the farewell (Shaharabani et al. 2018). Thus, from the first session onwards, the therapist must integrate both the development of the alliance and an awareness of eventual closure: this facilitates a functional, rather than abrupt, end to treatment, strengthening the patient's autonomy and validating the progress made.

ROLE PLAY IN THE CLINICAL CONTEXT

Role play has established itself as a useful tool in clinical practice to facilitate emotional exploration and understanding of relational patterns. This technique allows patients to act out meaningful situations, promoting the symbolic expression of internal conflicts and awareness of their emotions and behaviours (Greenberg 2004). In the first session, its use can help therapists observe the interpersonal dynamics of the client, identify resistance, and co-construct initial diagnostic hypotheses in a more experiential way.

In addition, recent studies on role-playing interventions highlight that these techniques increase patient involvement and promote insight by allowing the symbolic expression of internal conflicts (Jiang et al. 2023; Otani et al. 2024). In brief clinical contexts, role play offers an effective means of assessing emotions, promoting collaboration, and consolidating the early therapeutic relationship, a key predictor of treatment continuity and success (Flückiger et al. 2020).

METHODOLOGY

Based on the curriculum guidelines that were institutionally established in the various academic programmes, the specific competencies and learning outcomes (LO) that each student must achieve in each of the courses that comprise the programme are described. These must be consistent with knowledge, know-how and behaviour. Therefore, when developing and planning their classes, teachers must ensure that the assessment products are aligned with the specific competencies and LR established in the lesson plans.

The Student Practice I course is a learning space that ensures students develop clinical competencies within the legal, ethical, and research framework of the

profession, allowing them to carry out processes associated with the assessment and intervention of individuals and groups through psychological care, monitoring and recording clinical formats such as medical records, progress sheets, test reports, therapeutic process closure reports and withdrawal closure forms, which enable students to analyse and conceptualise clinical cases. (Cecar, 2025).

Within the course in question, specific competencies are essential, as they guide student learning. These are presented below: Assesses the psychological conditions of clients in order to establish an intervention plan tailored to their needs, taking into account their context, developmental stage, and individual characteristics through different assessment techniques in accordance with the conceptual framework of psychology. Intervene in the various problems that are the subject of clinical attention in individuals, providing tools and strategies that contribute to the mental health of those involved through the use of knowledge of the discipline, techniques, methods, and ethical and research principles (Cecar 2025).

Along the same lines, the learning outcomes (LO) covered in the course are described as follows: Initially, clinical histories are constructed using theory and scientific evidence in accordance with the needs of the patients in order to make a diagnostic impression and intervention, facilitating therapeutic care. Secondly, emphasis is placed on designing and executing intervention plans using psychotherapeutic techniques that respond to the needs identified in the client(s) (Cecar 2025).

In this vein, students in the course who are doing clinical practice focus mainly on the development of processes related to the care and evaluation of clinical cases, allowing them to have a meaningful learning experience in which they put into practice the skills and competencies that a therapist must have when carrying out an evaluation and intervention process.

On the other hand, it is important to highlight that within the methodology used, role-play stands out as the main purpose of this document within the framework of an innovative strategy that allows students to acquire therapeutic skills to conduct the first session as a fundamental part of their first approach to patient care. It is also important to mention that role-play is used in the course for the explanation and execution of the different therapeutic sessions. In addition, it allows for feedback on therapeutic skills, the appropriation of the first session guide, active listening, among others. In this sense, teachers constantly monitor the initial process, during and at the end of the clinical approach within the framework of what is established in clinical practice with the teaching-service modality according to Decree 2376 of 2010.

Before providing the guide for the first session developed for the Student Practice I course, it is necessary to specify relevant aspects that were taken into account for the clinical approach to the first encounter with patients, as well as how role-play contributes to students' clinical skills prior to psychological care. For this reason, it is necessary to specify the authors who support the guide:

According to Muñoz and Villegas (2017), role-play is extremely important in therapy, as it allows patients to take on a role and rehearse new forms of behaviour and explore emotions and interpersonal conflicts in a safe and controlled space. Along the same lines, not only as patients but also as therapists, students will be able to simulate a psychological session for feedback, facilitating the acquisition and appropriation of the specific skills expected in the course.

According to the journal *Clínica y Salud Mental* (1993), informed consent is an ethical and legal requirement of utmost importance, which ensures patient autonomy and promotes a trustworthy therapeutic environment. In effect, it is an initial and indispensable step in the clinical care approach, where students are instructed to ensure that patients understand, agree, and clarify any doubts, after which patients can fill in the date, signature, and fingerprint on the document.

Romero (n.d.) adds that the therapeutic framework allows limits and conditions to be established between patient and therapist, providing a space of trust and respect that will facilitate the therapeutic process. Subsequently, within psychological care, the reason for consultation follows, which, according to Pérez (2015), is the point that gives way to the therapeutic process, as it allows the therapist to interpret the patient's needs and the objectives to be evaluated during therapy.

After this, according to Martínez (2019), identifying the current problem is of utmost importance in order to understand the reason why the patient decided to attend therapy and to define the focus of attention for intervention. For this reason, it is extremely important to have therapeutic skills to break down the main symptoms. Added to this is the contribution of Konrad Lorenz University (2022), which mentions basic therapeutic skills such as empathy, active listening, synthesis, and paraphrasing, which must be present in therapy, as they are fundamental to establishing effective communication with the patient and strengthening the alliance created with them.

Thus, according to García and Herrero (2018), the therapeutic alliance is the main predictor of success in therapy, as a solid bond between patient and therapist facilitates the effectiveness of the intervention. Additionally, this will facilitate the formulation of diagnostic hypotheses and, according to Londoño (2018), is fundamental in psychological therapy, as it guides the therapist in

understanding the case and making clinical decisions, integrating relevant patient information in a coherent manner. Another aspect to bear in mind is the completion of the medical history. According to Ramos Pozón (2015), the medical history is a fundamental tool for gaining a comprehensive view of the patient, facilitating the analysis of factors and background information specific to the medical history.

To conclude psychological care with patients, the therapeutic skill of synthesis is essential, as noted by Feltham and Dryden (1993), which allows the therapist to integrate and interpret the most relevant aspects of the patient's discourse, which promotes understanding and progress in the patient's process, thus making them feel heard and understood. Finally, there is the therapeutic closure which, according to García (2016), allows the achievements made during the session to be consolidated and helps the patient to understand that the session has ended.

Now, we will break down the guide for the first session used in the Student Practice I course, allowing students to study it and then simulate how they will address the student acting as the patient or when they are with a real patient.

WELCOME GREETING AND INTRODUCTION OF THE TRAINEE PSYCHOLOGIST

In this section, you should bear in mind the importance of rapport and address the other person with respect, using formal language and avoiding informal terms.

INFORMED CONSENT

Good morning or good afternoon. Pleased to meet you, my name is (state your first and last name), I am a trainee psychologist and I will be attending to you today. Did reception give you the informed consent form? Did you bring a photocopy of your identity card?

I would like to inform you that the informed consent form is a document that, by signing it, you agree to receive psychological care. The confidentiality of the information will be guaranteed within this space. In relation to the activation of the route, this is done when warranted and consists of interdisciplinary work with other professionals. The advisor will join some of the sessions we will have, and we will both maintain confidentiality.

(After this, the patient is asked to fill in the date, signature and fingerprint, or these are verified. In the case of care for minors, the parents' signatures, dates and fingerprints are verified, and photocopies of the patient's identity cards and identity documents are also received).

THERAPEUTIC FRAMEWORK

Next, I will explain the therapeutic framework: Sessions are held on Mondays from 2:00 p.m. to 3:00 p.m., and each session lasts 60 minutes (a date and time were provided as an example). If you arrive a few minutes late for your session, you will be seen for the remaining time. If you miss two consecutive sessions without notifying the centre, you risk losing your place and being reassigned to another therapist. There is also an assessment phase, which consists of gathering information, administering psychological tests and returning the results. The intervention phase is an intervention plan that will allow you to acquire tools for the diagnosis found. (Strategically, you can ask if you have any questions or concerns at this point).

COLLECTION OF SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Sociodemographic data that is part of the medical history will now be collected. (All sociodemographic data from the medical history is requested, including the patient's name and close contact information. Remember that this must be completed in the first session).

REASON FOR CONSULTATION

At this point, I will ask you, 'What is the reason for your consultation?' (After this, listen carefully to the information provided by the patient, which will allow you to break down the aspects mentioned by the patient in the reason for consultation, for example: emotional, cognitive and behavioural dimensions, as well as aspects that clarify the before, during and after of the patient's current symptoms, and questions to measure frequency, intensity and duration).

EXPAND INFORMATION GATHERING

(When gathering all aspects related to the reason for the consultation, the following is explained to the patient): At this time, I would like to inform you that I will be asking you questions related to your medical history that will allow me to learn more about you.

(The questions asked should be guided by the questions for recording medical history. It is important that you appropriate therapeutic skills so that you can put them into practice during clinical care or simulation. Another aspect to take into account is the questions aimed at organising the history of the problem chronologically: childhood, adolescence, adulthood and the present. In addition, when changing the subject, it is suggested that you contextualise the new information you will be asking about).

SUMMARY OF THE SESSION AND CLOSING

Due to time constraints, the session has ended, and I would like to provide some feedback on today's work. Initially, we addressed informed consent, the

therapeutic framework, i.e., the rules and regulations of the practice, then the collection of sociodemographic data, and we broke down the reason for the consultation where these aspects are addressed (two or three main aspects are mentioned). In the next session, we will expand on this information, as well as aspects related to your medical history that will allow me to learn more about you. See you at the next session (the date and time of the meeting are given as appropriate).

Explanatory note

The information in italics will not be disclosed to the patient; it only contextualises what the trainee psychologist will do.

RESULTS

The Student Practice I course is part of the Teaching-Service agreement signed with a higher education institution, in which students carry out the clinical practice covered in the ninth semester, providing psychological care services to children, adolescents and adults. It is important to note that students in this course carry out their practice in a higher education setting with a different social purpose, where they rotate and participate in training spaces. They also carry out activities under the constant supervision of teachers, as established in the Teaching-Service agreement (Decree 2376, 2010).

In accordance with the above, the Student Practice I course is a space in which students, through role-play, strengthen and acquire the competencies and skills that will allow them to have their first contact with patient care. In this regard, the traceability of patients who accessed the Psychology service in the last two and a half years is noteworthy:

Table 2. Number of patients treated from 2023-I to 2025-I.

Period	Number of patients treated per semester	Number of patients treated per year	Number of treatments per year
2023-I	53	94	345
2023-II	41		
2024-I	40	91	348
2024-II	51		
2025-I	56	56	165

Source: Own elaboration

In this regard, 53 patients were treated in the 2023-I period, 41 patients in the 2023-II period, for a total of 94 patients in 2023, represented by 345 cases treated during that year. On the other hand, in the period corresponding to 2024-I, 40 patients were treated, and in the period 2024-II, 51 patients were treated, for a total of 91 patients in that year. In addition, for the period 2025-I, there were 56 patients, evidenced in 165 visits.

At this point, it is essential to highlight role-play as an innovative methodological strategy, which has allowed students to develop therapeutic skills and competencies during their professional practice. In contrast to the above, the feedback from teachers with the appropriate knowledge and experience in the clinical area stands out, since it focuses on strengthening therapeutic skills and competencies. In this way, the reason for consultation is addressed, highlighting the time, situation, signs, symptoms and problems in the patient's discourse, where the student engages in active listening, using guiding questions aimed at identifying the problem, among other aspects of the clinical approach.

DISCUSSION THE RESULTS

The integration of role-play in the first therapeutic session is in line with the theoretical framework that assigns a dual function to this encounter: assessment of the reason for consultation and establishment of the framework and alliance. By allowing the experiential representation of relevant situations, role-play facilitates the observation of interpersonal patterns and the co-construction of early diagnostic hypotheses, which complements the verbal clinical history and encourages the active involvement of the patient (Del Río et al. 2022).

From a training perspective, recent evidence on simulation and role-play learning shows clear benefits in the development of clinical skills: improved communication skills, empathy, self-confidence, and practical application of theoretical knowledge (Elendu et al. 2024; Wu et al. 2024). These results support the idea that role-play operationalises the therapeutic skills described in the framework (active listening, empathy, formulation) by offering deliberate practice with immediate feedback and structured evaluation.

Compared to previous research, studies with standardised patients and deliberate practice-based training report positive effects on observable skills, although mostly in simulated or teaching contexts (Kühne et al. 2020; Østergård et al. 2022). This is consistent with the review of simulations in health education, which shows improvements in non-technical skills but heterogeneous evidence of direct clinical effects in real patients.

Implementing role-play in the first session (or in initial simulated sessions with informed consent) can accelerate alliance building and provide valuable behavioural data for a preliminary diagnostic hypothesis, as well as serving as a training tool for students. However, its use requires a clear ethical framework, well-designed scripts, and supervision to avoid adverse effects (patient distancing or resistance). The literature highlights the need for reliable instruments to assess the quality of the therapeutic relationship and clinical changes after role-play interventions.

In terms of limitations, most recent studies evaluate training or simulated outcomes; there is a lack of controlled trials measuring real clinical consequences (longitudinally measured alliance, adherence, symptomatic reduction) when role-play is incorporated into the first session with real patients. Furthermore, methodological heterogeneity (types of role-play, duration, degree of directivity, role of standardised actors compared to peers) hinders robust synthesis.

For future lines of research, it is recommended to conduct randomised controlled trials comparing standard first sessions with first sessions using role-play on variables such as therapeutic alliance, insights, and symptomatology; to investigate moderators (therapist training level, type of disorder, role-play format); and to evaluate technological formats (standardised actors vs. virtual reality) to optimise efficacy and scalability. Multicentre studies and longitudinal measures would allow us to determine whether training benefits translate into better clinical outcomes in the medium and long term.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude the topics discussed above, it should be noted that they are of utmost importance not only for professionals in training, but also for those who wish to strengthen their knowledge through postgraduate courses that train therapists in the clinical field. In addition, it is necessary to document the clinical approach through role-play for the acquisition of therapeutic skills. Knowing the therapeutic framework, having active listening skills, and conducting a therapeutic closure, among other aspects mentioned in the article, such as guiding the first session, help in the acquisition of knowledge and enable effective, clear, and organised intervention.

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